

EFFECT OF BUERGER ALLEN EXERCISE ON THE VALUE OF ANKLE BRACHIAL INDEX IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE II DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract

Diabetes mellitus occurs due to an increase in blood glucose levels which results in complications in the form of peripheral arterial disease resulting in diabetic ulcers. In streamlining peripheral tissue perfusion can be done by doing Buerger Allen exercise which utilizes the force of gravity so that it plays a role in improving oxygen circulation in the arteries as evidenced by the increase in the value of the ankle brachial index from the results of dividing the systolic blood pressure of the foot (dorsalis pedis) with the systolic blood pressure of the arm (brachial). This study aims to determine the effectiveness of giving buerger allen exercise on changes in ankle brachial index values in patients with type II diabetes mellitus. This type of research is a quasy-experiment pre and post-test with control group, sampling technique using purposive sampling of 11 people/group. Data collection used ABI values to measure changes in values before and after BAE. Intervention was carried out 6 consecutive days with a duration of 15 minutes each meeting. The results of the study using the Paired T-test test showed that the ABI value of the intervention group obtained a p-value of 0.000 (<0.05), while the ABI value of the control group with a p-value of 0.783 (>0.05), so it can be concluded that there is a significant effectiveness between the administration of buerger allen exercise on changes in ankle brachial index values.

Keywords: Ankle brachial index, Buerger Allen exercise, Diabetes mellitus

1. INTRODUCTION

According to data from the International Diabetes Federation (2021), 537 adults aged 20-79 years or 1 in 10 people live with diabetes worldwide, Indonesia is the fifth country with a population of 179.72 million with 19.47 million suffering from diabetes, which means the prevalence of diabetes in Indonesia is 10.6% after China, India, Pakistan, and the United States. Based on Riskesdas, the prevalence of type II DM in Indonesia from 2013 to 2018 has increased from 6.9% to 8.5% (Kemenkes RI, 2018). The target number of DM patients in 2020 in Bandung City is 43,906 patients, of which 12,221 people are served in clinics or hospitals and their domicile cannot be determined (Bandung City Health Profile, 2020). The impact of increased blood sugar if not treated immediately will result in acute and even chronic complications. Acute complications that can occur in people with diabetes mellitus are changes in glucose levels, while chronic complications that can occur are changes in the

cardiovascular system, changes in the peripheral nervous system, changes in mood and increased susceptibility to infection (LeMone, Karen M. Burke, 2016). Chronic complications result from suboptimal management, causing macrovascular disorders and microvascular disorders. Macrovascular disorders are coronary heart disease (CHD), congestive heart failure, stroke and peripheral arterial disease (PAD), while microvascular disorders are diabetic nephropathy, retinopathy (blindness) and neuropathy (Smeltzer & Bare, 2015). Peripheral arterial disease is an impaired blood supply to the upper or lower extremities due to obstruction (Beshyah, 2014) and the majority of obstruction is caused by atherosclerosis, but can also be caused by thrombosis, embolism, vasculitis, or fibromuscular dysplasia (Brady, A-M., McCabe, C & McCann, 2014). The prevalence of PAD in the world is estimated to be more than 202 million people with individuals aged ≥ 40 years being 4.3% and those aged ≥ 70 years being 14.5% (WHO, 2016). The prevalence of PAD in Indonesia in one million Indonesians, 13,807 people suffer from PAD (Said et al., 2021). Damage to the peripheral nerves will result in ulcers, gangrene, impaired perfusion of the lower extremities, slow wound blockage and even amputation (Putu et al., 2021). To detect the possibility of peripheral circulation disorders, the ankle brachial index is measured, which is obtained by dividing the systolic blood pressure of the foot (dorsalis pedis) by the systolic blood pressure of the arm (brachial) (Salam & Laili, 2020).

Actions to improve peripheral tissue perfusion are foot care, wearing special shoes for diabetics, diabetic foot exercises, mobility exercises and Buerger Allen Exercise (BAE) (El-Fattah et al., 2019). These activities can not only improve blood flow, but also make people with diabetes mellitus feel comfortable and relaxed. Created by Leo Buerger in 1926 and Arthur Allen in 1930, BAE is a modality therapy performed with various active postural movements in the plantar area. Through BAE stimulation of muscle contractions, position changes, and postural exercises that can play a role in improving oxygen circulation in the arteries and circulation in the lower limbs (Chang et al., 2016). The mechanism of BAE is by changing gravity, applied position and muscle pump by active movement of the ankle for smooth muscle blood vessels. Gravity helps empty and fill the blood column alternately, thus improving vascular transportation which can prevent peripheral vascular disease (Hasina et al., 2021). Muscle Pump has a mechanism, namely the movement of leg muscles using the gravitational force of the feet (Pebrianti, 2018). Buerger Allen exercise intervention must be done regularly so that blood vessels will experience vasodilation so that blood volume becomes better in the peripheral area. This is in line with research conducted by (Hafid et al., 2021) showing the results of Wilcoxon signed-rank test the ABI value on the right limb is 0.043 or $P < 0.05$ and the ABI value on the left is 0.025 or $p < 0.05$. So it can be concluded that buerger allen exercise is effective for use as an intervention and treatment for patients with diabetes mellitus who experience peripheral tissue perfusion damage. Meanwhile, research conducted at Selected University Hospital-Egypt by El-Fattah et al (2019) showed that after the intervention the mean value of the ABI score of both limbs was (right leg = 1.097, left leg: 1.086) which showed a higher significance value compared to the score before the intervention (right leg = 0.885, left leg = 0.937). Researchers when guiding students who are conducting comprehensive nursing clinical practice at UPT Ciparay Health Center, obtained the results of a preliminary study of 80 people suffering from diabetes mellitus. Based on the current phenomenon, DM sufferers at the Ciparay Puskesmas DTP are increasing. The results of interviews conducted with DM patients at the Ciparay Puskesmas DTP, there were 7 people experiencing complaints such as cramps, tingling, numbness, coldness in the legs and even wounds and impaired healing, Many type II DM sufferers still do not know and ignore the symptoms of peripheral circulation damage. Therefore, it is important to conduct an ABI

examination to determine peripheral circulation damage in patients with DM because in the Ciparay Puskesmas DTP there is no program in this ABI examination and the provision of BAE intervention as one of the physical activities that can prevent PAD. Therefore, researchers are interested in conducting research with the title "The Effect of Giving Buerger Allen Exercise on Ankle Brachial Index Values in Patients with Type II Diabetes Mellitus at Ciparay Health Center DTP".

2. METHODOLOGY

This type of research is included in the type of research that is quantitative. This study used a quasy-experiment pre and post-test with control group research design to compare the effectiveness of the intervention given to the treatment group with the control group before and after the intervention. The population in this study were patients with type II diabetes mellitus at the Ciparay Health Center DTP, totaling 50 people. The number of samples was calculated based on Federer (1991) cited by David & Arkeman (2018) with the formula $(n-1)(t-1) > 15$, obtained 22 divided into 2 groups. The sampling technique in this study used purposive sampling, by setting inclusion and exclusion criteria. Some of the criteria determined to qualify the study include the following: Inclusion Criteria (Type II diabetes mellitus patients who actively follow the prolanis program, DM patients who do not have a history of heart disease, DM patients with stable hemodynamics <150 mmHg, patients who have DM within the last 5-10 years.

Exclusion criteria: Patients who are not willing to be respondents and patients who are not cooperative. The instruments used in collecting data for this study were standard operating procedures (SOP) buerger allen exercise and observation sheets. ankle brachial index value. In this study, univariate analysis that has been carried out is used to answer the research objectives, namely the description of the value of blood sugar during and the description of the value of the ankle brachial index in patients with type II DM before and after the buerger allen exercise. Bivariate analysis was carried out to prove the research hypothesis, namely the effectiveness of giving Buerger Allen exercise on changes in the value of the ankle brachial index. In this analysis, data normality test was conducted first using the Shapiro Wilk test, because the sample was less than 50 samples ($N < 50$) and the results showed normal distributed data ($p > 0.05$). Furthermore, a parametric paired sample t-test was carried out to identify the average difference before and after the intervention with alpha 0.05 or 95% confidence level which was processed with a computer program and obtained a p value in the Sig (2-tailed) column < 0.05 in the intervention group, so H_0 was rejected while the p value > 0.05 in the control group, so H_0 was accepted so that there was effectiveness from the research that had been done.

3. RESULTS

The results of the distribution and percentage study described are data on blood sugar values and ankle brachial index values and comparison of the effectiveness of ankle brachial index values before and after giving buerger allen exercise.

3.1 Frequency Distribution of Blood Sugar Values Before Giving Buerger Allen Exercise to Patients with Type II DM

Table 1: Blood Sugar Value Before Buerger Allen Exercise.

Variabel Penelitian	Kategori	Intervensi		Kontrol	
		N	%	N	%
Gula Darah Pre					
<70	Rendah	0	0%	0	0%
70-200	Normal	4	36,4%	7	63,6%
>200	Tinggi	7	63,6%	4	36,4%
Jumlah		11	100%	11	100%

Based on table 3.1 shows that the frequency distribution of blood sugar values during DM patients at Ciparay Health Center DTP before giving buerger allen exercise in the intervention group was in the high category as much as 63.6%, while the control group had normal blood sugar values as much as 63.6%.

3.2 Frequency Distribution of Blood Sugar Values After Giving Buerger Allen Exercise to Patients with Type II DM at Ciparay Health Center DTP

Table 2: Blood Sugar Value After Buerger Allen Exercise.

Variabel Penelitian	Kategori	Intervensi		Kontrol	
		N	%	N	%
Gula Darah Post					
<70	Rendah	0	0%	0	0%
70-200	Normal	3	27,3%	7	63,6%
>200	Tinggi	8	72,7%	4	36,4%
Jumlah		11	100%	11	100%

Based on table 2 shows that the frequency distribution of blood sugar values during Type II DM patients at Ciparay Health Center DTP after giving buerger allen exercise in the intervention group in the high category as much as 72.7%, while the control group had normal blood sugar values as much as 63.6%.

3.3 Frequency Distribution of Ankle Brachial Index Values Before Giving Buerger Allen Exercise to Patients with Type II DM at Ciparay Health Center DTP

Table 3: Ankle Brachial Index Value Before Buerger Allen Exercise

Variabel Penelitian	Kategori	Intervensi		Kontrol	
		n	%	n	%
Nilai ABI Pre					
>1.3	<i>Elevated, incompressible vessels</i>	0	0%	1	9,1%
0,91-1,30	Normal	2	18,2%	4	36,4%
0.70-0.90	<i>Borderline Perfusion</i>	9	81,8%	6	54,5%
0.40-0,69	<i>Severe ischemia</i>	0	0%	0	0%
<0.4	<i>Critical ischemia, limb threatened</i>	0	0%	0	0%
Jumlah		11	100%	11	100%

Table 3 shows that the frequency distribution of ankle brachial index values of Type II DM patients at Ciparay Health Center DTP before giving buerger allen exercise in the intervention group in the borderline perfusion category as much as 81.8% while in the control group in the normal category as much as 54.4%.

3.4 Frequency Distribution of Ankle Brachial Index Values After Giving Buerger Allen Exercise to Patients with Type II DM at Ciparay Health Center DTP

Table 4: Ankle Brachial Index Value After Buerger Allen Exercise

Nilai ABI Post	Kategori	Intervensi		Kontrol	
		n	%	n	%
>1.3	Elevated, incompressible vessels	0	0%	1	9%
0,91-1,30	Normal	9	81,8%	5	45,5%
0.70-0.90	Borderline Perfusion	2	18,2%	5	45,5%
0.40-0,69	Severe ischemia	0	0%	0	0%
<0.4	Critical ischemia, limb threatened	0	0%	0	0%
Jumlah		11	100%	11	100%

Based on table 4 shows that the frequency distribution of ankle brachial index values of Type II DM patients at Ciparay Health Center DTP after giving buerger allen exercise in the intervention group in the normal category was 81.8% and in the control group in the normal category was 45.5%. while borderline perfusion was 45.5%.

3.5 Bivariate Test Results Paired T-Test Effectiveness of Buerger Allen Exercise on Changes in Ankle Brachial Index Value in Patients with Type II DM at Ciparay Health Center DTP

Table 5: Effectiveness of Buerger Allen Exercise on Changes in Ankle Brachial Index

Kelompok	Mean		Std. Deviation		Paired T-Test	P Value
	Pre-test	Post-test	Pre-test	Post-test		
Intervensi	0.845	0.982	0.1572	0.1601	0.000	<0.05 Signifikan
Kontrol	0.991	0.973	0.2625	0.1555	0.783	>0.05 Tidak Signifikan

Based on the analysis of table 5, the results of statistical tests using Paired T-Test show that the mean in the pre-test intervention group is 0.845 and post-test is 0.982 with the results of the p value = 0.000 or $p < 0.05$, meaning that there is a significant change in the value of the ankle brachial index in DM patients before and after giving Buerger Allen exercise. While the mean in the control group pre-test 0.991 and post-test 0.973 with the results of p value = 0.783 or $p > 0.05$ means that there is no significant change in the value of the ankle brachial index in DM patients before and after giving Buerger Allen exercise

4. CONCLUSIONS

The results showed that the Ankle Brachial Index (ABI) value of the intervention group before being given the intervention obtained a mean of 0.845 then after being given the

intervention obtained a mean of 0.982 with a p-value of 0.000 (<0.05), while the ABI value of the control group before being given the intervention obtained a mean of 0.991 then after being given the intervention obtained a mean of 0.973 with a p-value of 0.783 (>0.05), so it can be concluded that there is a significant effectiveness between giving buerger allen exercise on changes in Ankle Brachial Index (ABI) values. The results of this study can be used as a prevention of complications of diabetes mellitus in reducing the incidence of Peripheral Artery Disease (PAD).

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